

LLM Experiments with Programmable Matter: Preliminary Studies with SP-CellBots

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Abstract

This research note is framed as a snapshot of an early phase of LLM-assisted interaction with programmable matter. It investigates how well current general-purpose LLMs, without dedicated 3D training, can analyze modular bot clusters, devise spatial strategies, execute them, and assess the outcome via the SP-CellBots API. To this end, compact preliminary studies on replication, wall repair, morphology recognition, and functional Shepherd scenarios are documented. The experiments show that modern models already provide remarkably usable responses to simple 3D and control tasks, especially when clear API feedback and structured prompts are available. At the same time, more complex spatial tasks remain prone to orientation errors, incomplete planning, and issues with connectivity or shape preservation. The research note therefore documents not only results, but also a contemporary snapshot of the opportunities and limitations of LLMs in modular robotics.

1 Introduction

This research note documents a snapshot: How well can current general-purpose LLMs, without dedicated 3D training, use the SP-CellBots API to analyze a modular bot cluster, develop strategies for spatial tasks, execute them, and then evaluate the results? The underlying basis is the SP-CellBots platform Pohl 2025 together with the Opcode protocol Pohl 2026a. The emphasis is deliberately on preliminary studies rather than a full statistical investigation. The goal is not a large benchmark, but a traceable look at how models today handle voxel structures, coordinates, and API feedback.

This snapshot also has a historical character. Models and model versions change very quickly; capabilities that are only rudimentary today may become commonplace within a few years. For that reason, it is worthwhile to record the current limits of LLMs in CAD-, Blender-, and robotics-adjacent 3D tasks now. The present study therefore also acts as a temporal document: it records which kinds of 3D voxel problems current LLMs still struggle with and how they respond to such tasks.

In this context, the SP-CellBots API serves as a clear and as simple as possible gateway to a 3D bot cluster. For evaluation, not only the final result matters, but also the solution path: Does the model recognize the structure correctly? Does it use diagnostic functions? Does it confuse copying with moving? Does it respond to blocked paths by replanning, aborting, or violating rules? These differences are especially revealing in the present study.

Aus dieser Perspektive ergeben sich vier kompakte Experimentfamilien:

- **Structure replication:** recognize an object and rebuild it elsewhere;
- **LLM auto-repair:** detect and repair defects, gaps, and instabilities;
- **Morphology recognition:** describe, classify, and interpret structures functionally;
- **Shepherd problems:** solve functional tasks such as enclosures, bridges, barriers, or rescue scenarios.

The Shepherd problems form the central thread of the paper. They bundle simple but expressive tasks in which an LLM does not merely reproduce a shape, but transforms a spatial situation under functional and safety-related constraints into a useful configuration. This is also where the value of the SP-CellBots platform as a simulation environment becomes clear: it makes it possible to run such preliminary studies with well-defined initial states, well-documented prompts, and reproducible API feedback.

2 Experiments

2.0.1 Structure Replication

Zykov et al. Zykov et al. (2005) showed early on with *Molecubes* how modular units can be combined into self-replicating structures. The scenario considered here is only loosely inspired by that work: a tower four bots high is to be replicated three cells in the x -direction without moving the original structure. The full prompt is documented in Appendix A.

```
Experiment: Copy Object +3 in X Direction

Mobility mode: vehicle_kinematics (VK)
Scenario: A cluster of modular cube robots is standing on a flat base at y=0.
On top of this base (y>=1) there is an object (e.g. a tower, a cross, a wall).
The goal is to rebuild this object as a copy shifted by +3 in x-direction.
...
```

Even a seemingly simple tower poses non-trivial planning questions for LLMs: dismantling and rebuilding must happen in the correct order, the upper bot must not be moved before the lower one, and the geometry of the target position must match the F-side rule. This is exactly where it becomes clear that the model does not bring any built-in block-toy intuition, but must derive its strategy from the prompt, diagnostics, and feedback.

The model responses differ mainly in style: Deepseek worked more diagnostically and checked the spatial arrangement in very small steps, while ChatGPT switched to a donor-bot strategy earlier.

(a) Initial scene

(b) Intermediate state

Figure 1: Initial scene and intermediate state of the replication task.

Target	Structure	Deepseek V4 Flash	ChatGPT Codex	Observation
2	L-shape	✓ Successful	✓ Successful	Both models replicated the structure with donor bots without modifying the original.
3	2x2 block	✓ Successful	✓ Successful	Both models produced an exact copy at $x + 2$.
4	Plus shape	~ Partial	~ Partial	The offset caused an overlap with the original structure; both models detected the geometric blockage.

Table 1: Condensed results of the structure replication task.

The additional replication series shows above all that both models understand the basic idea of a copy, but execute the spatial planning differently. Deepseek remained more diagnostic, while ChatGPT switched to the donor-bot strategy earlier. The plus-shape experiment remains a partial success because of the overlap.

2.0.2 Detecting Structures and Repairing Walls

As the test structure, a 5×4 wall on the $z = 3$ plane was presented with a single bot missing at position $(4, 3, 3)$. The task was to detect the defect, choose a suitable donor bot, and then close the wall again. The prompt therefore mainly required structural analysis, planning, and a clean return to the original state.

The full prompt for this experiment is documented in the web links at the end Pohl 2026b.

All four models recognized the gap correctly and solved the task without follow-up questions. Deepseek was the most diagnostic and completed the experiment in YOLO mode after 7,6 seconds. After the repair step, the donor bot used was returned to its original position in each case.

Model	Finding	Repair	Brief observation	Result
Deepseek V4 Flash	Wall with hole	Hole at (4, 3, 3)	Diagnostic, fastest run	✓
ChatGPT Codex 5.4-Mini	Wall with hole	Hole at (4, 3, 3)	Successful and stable	✓
Gemini 3.5 Flash	Wall with hole	Hole at (4, 3, 3)	Successful without detours	✓
Claude Opus 4.6	Wall with hole	Hole at (4, 3, 3)	Successful; donor bot reset	✓

Table 2: Experiment 02: wall with hole. All models recognized the defect and closed the wall with a donor bot.

Figure 2: Initial state of Experiment 02: a 5×4 wall with a gap.

2.0.3 Recognizing the Morphology of Simple Structures

In Experiment 03, six simple SP-CellBots structures were presented: a stepped shape, T-shape, table or platform, square frame, E-shape, and a little figure. The goal was not a perfect CAD analysis, but a robust morphological classification based on the API data.

The full prompt for this experiment is documented in the web links at the end Pohl 2026c.

Both models recognized most shapes reliably. The main uncertainty arose with the E-shape, which ChatGPT initially interpreted as a G- or hook-like form. Overall, the experiment shows that LLMs can already describe simple 3D morphologies well, but still fluctuate when shapes are symbolic or stylized.

Structure	Deepseek	ChatGPT Codex	Brief finding
Steps / ziggurat	✓	✓	Both correct; Deepseek: ziggurat, ChatGPT: stepped structure.
T-shape	✓	✓	Both correctly recognized as a T-shape.
Table / platform	✓	✓	Both correctly recognized as a table or platform on supports.
Square / frame	✓	✓	Both correctly recognized as a hollow frame or O-shape.
E-shape	✓	~	Deepseek correct; ChatGPT initially G/hook, later E.
Little figure	✓	✓	Both recognized as a figurative structure.

Table 3: Results of Experiment 03: morphology recognition of simple SP-CellBots structures. ✓ = correctly recognized, ~ = partially correct or only classified correctly after follow-up questions.

Figure 3: Six example figures for Experiment 03.

2.1 Shepherd Experiments

The Shepherd experiments serve as a good analogy for managing a "herd" of many independent elements: they must be shielded, sealed, bridged, rescued, kept together, or transformed into a new shape. For these preliminary studies, Deepseek `deepseek-v4-flash` and ChatGPT 5.4-Mini (`high`) were tested; this is explicitly a qualitative probe, not a full benchmark.

2.1.1 Shepherd-1: Shield / Barn

Shepherd-1 tests a simple shielding task: a target bot is to be completely enclosed by neighboring bots. The full prompt is documented in the web links at the end Pohl 2026d.

Model	Target recognized	Result	Observation
Deepseek V4 Flash	✓	✓	Target bot R46 fully enclosed; after prompt refinement, distant donor bots from the $x \geq 9$ region were used.
ChatGPT Codex 5.4-Mini	✓	✓	Target bot fully enclosed; however, nearby donor bots were used, which required recalibration of addresses and a <code>structurescan</code> .

Table 4: Results of Shepherd-1: Shield / Barn. Both models could fully shield the target bot using orthogonally adjacent bots.

Figure 4: The fictional "sheep" in the *Shield / Barn* setup with five free orthogonal neighborhood positions for complete enclosure.

2.1.2 Shepherd-2: Seal

Shepherd-2 tests the closing of a gap in an existing boundary. The full prompt is documented in the web links at the end Pohl 2026e.

Model	Gap recognized	Result	Observation
Deepseek V4 Flash	✓	✓	Detected the gap at $(3,1,3)$ and closed it efficiently with a single donor bot.
ChatGPT Codex 5.4-Mini	✓	✓	Initially interpreted the defect as a larger area to fill and used several bots; later recognized that the actual gap had already been closed.

Table 5: Results of Shepherd-2: Seal. Both models could close the boundary structure, but differed significantly in material efficiency.

(a) Task setup

(b) ChatGPT solution

Figure 5: Shepherd-2: Seal experiment. The left side shows the initial situation with the gap to be closed; the right side shows an example of the solution generated by ChatGPT.

2.1.3 Shepherd-3: Bridge

Shepherd-3 checks whether a load-bearing bridge can be built between two elevated pins. The full prompt is documented in the web links at the end Pohl 2026f.

Model	Bridge form recognized	Result	Observation
Deepseek V4 Flash	✓	✓	Built a complete L-shaped bridge with a corner at (9, 1, 1); used 8 donor bots and briefly tried to smooth resulting gaps afterwards, but then ended the experiment correctly.
ChatGPT Codex 5.4-Mini	✓	✓	Built the same L-shaped bridge with a corner at (9, 1, 1); also used 8 donor bots, but chose them closer to the master bot and completed the experiment without unnecessary corrections.

Table 6: Results of Shepherd-3: Bridge. Both models successfully built an orthogonal L-shaped bridge between the two pins.

Figure 6: Shepherd-3: Bridge experiment. The two initial pins (marked in blue) are shown, together with an example of the finished L-shaped bridge in the variant generated by Deepseek.

2.1.4 Shepherd-4: Rescue

Shepherd-4 is a rescue task: a sheepdog bot grasps a sheep from behind, transports it into the target gate, and then returns. Both models solved the task; Deepseek briefly needed an orientation correction. The full prompt is documented in the web links at the end Pohl 2026g.

Model	Payload recognized	Result	Observation
Deepseek V4 Flash	✓	✓	Recognized the sheep, gate center, and sheepdog; after a small orientation problem, the sheep was successfully brought into the gate and the sheepdog returned to the starting point.
ChatGPT Codex 5.4-Mini	✓	✓	Planned the sequence very smoothly, positioned the sheepdog behind the sheep, grasped the payload, and brought it into the target gate without visible obstacles.

Table 7: Results of Shepherd-4: Rescue. Both models could transport the sheep into the target gate and then return the sheepdog.

Figure 7: Shepherd-4: Rescue setup. The sheepdog bot marked in blue is supposed to grasp the sheep marked in green with the B-slot and transport it into the target gate marked on the left.

2.1.5 Shepherd-5: Slime-Mold Movement

Shepherd-5 models a connected herd that can only move through continuous material flow. This is where the tension between connectivity and shape preservation became most apparent. The full prompt is documented in the web links at the end Pohl 2026h.

Model	Connectivity maintained	Result	Observation
Deepseek V4 Flash	~	✓	Briefly violated the orthogonal connectivity rule during the second move, recognized the error, and corrected it; afterwards the remaining moves followed the rules.
ChatGPT Codex 5.4-Mini	✓	~	Kept connectivity in every move, but temporarily lost the target specification of the original 2×3 shape and initially produced more of a shifted chain.

Table 8: Results of Shepherd-5: Slime-Mold Movement. Both models had difficulty maintaining connectivity and shape preservation at the same time.

(a) Target formation after the Deepseek run

(b) Intermediate state in the ChatGPT run

Figure 8: Shepherd-5: Slime-Mold Movement. The left side shows the target formation reached by Deepseek; the bots marked in blue indicate the original position of the structure. The right side shows an example of the snake-like, connected intermediate structure during the ChatGPT run.

2.1.6 Writing

Shepherd-6 is no longer a pure herd task, but a symbolic shape task: the bots are supposed to form a readable A . The compact-herd analogy only remains loosely in the background here. The full prompt is documented in the web links at the end Pohl 2026i.

Model	Symbol recognized	Result	Observation
Deepseek V4 Flash	✓	✓	Produced a readable A , but initially chose nearby donor bots; as a result, gaps appeared in the base and several replanning steps were necessary.
ChatGPT Codex 5.4-Mini	✓	✓	Planned the setup more thoroughly, chose distant donor bots, and wrote the A as a 5×5 matrix without major incidents.

Table 9: Results of Shepherd-6: Writing and symbolic shape formation. Both models could generate a readable A , but differed in donor selection, stability, and chosen pixel matrix.

(a) Deepseek: 4×5 -Matrix

(b) ChatGPT: 5×5 -Matrix

Figure 9: Shepherd-6: Writing. Both models generated a readable A .

3 Concluding Remarks on the Classification of the Experiments

The experiments show SP-CellBots as an open field of investigation for LLM-assisted 3D interaction. Even simple tasks can trigger complex agentic chains of behavior.

The research note therefore understands itself as a snapshot: not a full benchmark study, but a qualitative documentation of how current models handle voxel structures, diagnostic messages, and spatial planning.

A Prompt for LLM-driven SP-CellBots Experiments

The following prompt was given to the investigated LLMs as a complete instruction set. It contains the description of the mobility mode, the available API commands, core safety rules, and the concrete task of replicating a simple structure. Since the results depend strongly on these instructions, the prompt is documented in full.

```
You are an agent for control, monitoring and diagnosis of a modular robot cluster (SP-CellBots).

Mobility mode: vehicle_kinematics (VK)

The units are mobile cubes that can move forward or backward along their front side (F-slot). Direction changes require a 90-degree rotation. The bots can stack on top of each other, climb down, and ascend or descend walls made of identical units.

Important movement rule: In VK mode, a bot can only move if its F-side points in the movement direction. Without the correct orientation, the path planner will fail (NO_SURFACE_PATH_FOUND). The target orientation can be passed as optional parameters vx vy vz to move_bot_to and diagnose_move_bot_to.

Important stacking rule: Always dismantle from top to bottom (highest bot first) and build from bottom to top (with ground contact at y =0). If you remove a bot that carries others, you will tear the cluster apart.

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```

API Commands (ordered by priority)

1. Orientation and Status

node api.js get_status

-> Query system status (bot count, mobility mode)

node api.js get_bot_position <id>

-> Get position and orientation of a single bot

node api.js get_bots_in_region <x1> <y1> <z1> <x2> <y2> <z2>

-> Scan all bots inside a 3D bounding box (ID + position). Essential for structure recognition!

node api.js is_occupied <x> <y> <z>

-> Check if a grid cell is occupied, returns bot ID and orientation

node api.js get_neighbors <id>

-> Show direct neighbors of a bot in all 6 slots (F/R/B/L/T/D)

2. Planning and Diagnosis (run before every action!)

node api.js diagnose_move_bot_to <id> <x> <y> <z> [vx] [vy] [vz]

-> Simulate a move. Shows path_found, would_split_cluster and disconnected_bots. Always run this first!

node api.js diagnose_move_carrier_to <id> <x> <y> <z>

-> Simulate a carrier move (with payload)

node api.js find_path_for_bot <id> <x> <y> <z> [vx] [vy] [vz]

-> Calculate path, actions and intermediate steps (more detailed than diagnose)

3. Execution

node api.js move_bot_to <id> <x> <y> <z> [vx] [vy] [vz]

-> Move a bot to a target position with optional target orientation. The orientation is often the key to successful pathfinding!

node api.js rotate_bot <id> <L/R>

-> Rotate a bot 90 degrees left or right

node api.js rotate_bot_to <id> <vx> <vy> <vz>

-> Rotate a bot to an absolute target orientation

node api.js grab_bot <carrier_id> <slot>

-> Pick up a bot (B-slot in VK mode)

node api.js release_bot <id>

-> Release a carried bot

4. Morphing (Structure Transformation)

node api.js morph_get_structures

-> List available target structures

node api.js morph_get_algos

-> List available morph algorithms (recommended: parallel_vehicle_kinematics)

node api.js morph_start <algo> <structure>

-> Start morph calculation and execution

node api.js morph_check_progress

-> Check morph progress (calculation_success -> finished)

5. Infrastructure

node api.js structurescan

-> Start Scan Level 1 for active structure discovery

node api.js recalibrate_bot_addresses

-> Recalculate bot addresses after structural changes

node api.js get_bots_in_region 0 1 0 20 20 20

-> Quick scan of all bots above y=0

node api.js batch <file.json>

-> Execute multiple move commands sequentially from a JSON file

Important Rules of Conduct

1. Diagnose first! Always run diagnose_move_bot_to before move_bot_to. Check would_split_cluster!

2. F-side rule: The target orientation (vx vy vz) is not optional for complex paths. Without the correct orientation the path planner will often fail.

3. Dismantle from top to bottom, build from bottom to top.

4. Reserve bots from y=0 can be used for new construction. Check with would_split_cluster first whether they carry other bots.

5. Check orientation with get_bot_position before planning a move.

B Prompt for a Copy Experiment / Replication

Experiment: Copy Object +3 in X Direction

Mobility mode: vehicle_kinematics (VK)

Scenario: A cluster of modular cube robots is standing on a flat base at $y=0$.

On top of this base ($y>=1$) there is an object (e.g. a tower, a cross, a wall).

The goal is to rebuild this object as a copy shifted by +3 in x-direction.

Important rules the simulator does NOT enforce (you must follow them yourself):

- Gravity acts in $-y$ direction. Bots without support below them are disconnected.
- When dismantling a stack, always start from the highest element.
- When building a stack, always place the lowest element first (must have ground contact at $y=0$).
- A bot can only climb if its F-side (front slot) points in the direction of movement. Without the correct orientation, the path planner will return `NO_SURFACE_PATH_FOUND`.
- Before every move, run `diagnose_move_bot_to`. Check: `path_found` AND `would_split_cluster`.
- If `would_split_cluster` is true, the move would tear the structure apart. Do NOT execute it!
- Use bots from $x=6, y=0$ as donors for the new structure. Leave existing structure bots untouched.

Step-by-step procedure:

1. Get an overview:

Run: `node api.js get_status`

Run: `node api.js get_bots_in_region 0 1 0 20 10 20`

This shows all bots at $y>=1$ (the object) and their positions.

2. Identify the object structure:

All bots at $y>=1$ form the object. Count them and note their positions.

Each bot will be moved +3 in x-direction.

Example: a bot at (2,1,3) moves to (5,1,3), a bot at (2,4,3) moves to (5,4,3).

3. Dismantle from top to bottom:

Start with the bot that has the highest y-coordinate. If multiple bots share the same height, you may choose any.

For each bot:

a) Run: `node api.js diagnose_move_bot_to <id> <x+3> <y> <z> [vx] [vy] [vz]`

The target orientation ($v_x v_y v_z$) is important. If the bot needs to climb, its F-side must point in the climbing direction.

b) Check that `path_found` is true and `would_split_cluster` is false.

c) If `would_split_cluster` is true: the bot carries another bot above it. Start with a different (higher) bot instead.

d) If `path_found` is false: try again with a different target orientation ($v_x v_y v_z$).

e) Run: `node api.js move_bot_to <id> <x+3> <y> <z> [vx] [vy] [vz]`

f) Confirm success.

4. If additional bots are needed for the new position:

Use donor bots from $x=6, y=0$.

Run: `node api.js get_bots_in_region 6 0 0 6 0 10`

This lists all available donor bots.

Check with `diagnose_move_bot_to` whether the donor can reach the target position.

Build from bottom to top: place the lowest y-level first.

5. Completion:

Run: `node api.js get_bots_in_region 0 1 0 20 10 20`

Compare the structure at the new x-position (original x +3) with the original structure.

All bots must be present. There must be no additional bots on $y>=1$.

6. Report:

Print a success message: "Experiment complete: Object successfully copied +3 in x-direction."

Add your assessment of the object's morphology (e.g. "The object is a single stack of 4 bots forming a tower" or "The object forms a cross/plus shape with 5 bots" or "The object is a 5x4 wall with 20 bots").

If the experiment was not fully successful, describe exactly which step failed and why.

References

- Pohl, Sven (2025). *SP-CellBots: Secure OPCODE Framework for Modular Robotics and Programmable Matter*. GitHub repository. Open-source reference implementation under the MIT License. URL: <https://github.com/svenpohl/sp-cellbots>.
- (Apr. 2026a). *A Modular and Secure Opcode Protocol for Programmable Matter*. Zenodo, Version 1.0, published April 11, 2026. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.19509605](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19509605). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19509605>.
- Zykov, Victor et al. (2005). “Self-Reproducing Machines”. In: *Nature* 435.7038, pp. 163–164. DOI: [10.1038/435163a](https://doi.org/10.1038/435163a).

Web Links

- Pohl, Sven (2026b). *Experimental Prompt for Experiment 02: Structure Inspection and Repair*. Full prompt used for Experiment 02: Wand reparieren. URL: https://github.com/svenpohl/sp-cellbots/blob/main/botcontroller/tests/prompt_cluster_control_exp02.txt (visited on 05/31/2026).
- (2026c). *Experimental Prompt for Experiment 03: Structure Description*. Full prompt used for Experiment 03: Morphologie einfacher Strukturen erkennen. URL: https://github.com/svenpohl/sp-cellbots/blob/main/botcontroller/tests/prompt_cluster_control_exp03.txt (visited on 05/31/2026).
 - (2026d). *Experimental Prompt for Experiment 04: Shepherd-1 Barn / Shield*. Full prompt used for Experiment 04: Shepherd-1 Barn / Shield. URL: https://github.com/svenpohl/sp-cellbots/blob/main/botcontroller/tests/prompt_cluster_control_exp04.txt (visited on 05/31/2026).
 - (2026e). *Experimental Prompt for Experiment 05: Shepherd-2 Seal*. Full prompt used for Experiment 05: Shepherd-2 Seal. URL: https://github.com/svenpohl/sp-cellbots/blob/main/botcontroller/tests/prompt_cluster_control_exp05.txt (visited on 05/31/2026).
 - (2026f). *Experimental Prompt for Experiment 06: Shepherd-3 Bridge*. Full prompt used for Experiment 06: Shepherd-3 Bridge. URL: https://github.com/svenpohl/sp-cellbots/blob/main/botcontroller/tests/prompt_cluster_control_exp06.txt (visited on 05/31/2026).
 - (2026g). *Experimental Prompt for Experiment 07: Shepherd-4 Rescue*. Full prompt used for Experiment 07: Shepherd-4 Rescue. URL: https://github.com/svenpohl/sp-cellbots/blob/main/botcontroller/tests/prompt_cluster_control_exp07.txt (visited on 05/31/2026).
 - (2026h). *Experimental Prompt for Experiment 08: Shepherd-5 Slime-Mold Movement*. Full prompt used for Experiment 08: Shepherd-5 Slime-Mold Movement. URL: https://github.com/svenpohl/sp-cellbots/blob/main/botcontroller/tests/prompt_cluster_control_exp08.txt (visited on 05/31/2026).
 - (2026i). *Experimental Prompt for Experiment 09: Shepherd-6 Writing*. Full prompt used for Experiment 09: Schreiben. URL: https://github.com/svenpohl/sp-cellbots/blob/main/botcontroller/tests/prompt_cluster_control_exp09.txt (visited on 05/31/2026).